

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STRATEGIES FOR THE REINTEGRATION OF DEFERRED AND EXCLUDED BLOOD DONORS AND BLOOD SUPPLY SUSTAINABILITY (2020–2024)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Temporarily deferred and permanently rejected blood donors represent both a safety necessity and an untapped strategic reserve. International evidence shows that structured re-entry pathways can recover a significant share of deferred donors without compromising safety.

Objective: To analyze the 2020–2024 donor deferral data and propose an integrated reintegration framework adapted to the Bulgarian transfusion context.

Methods: Secondary analysis of two cohorts: temporarily deferred ($n \approx 5355$) and permanently rejected ($n = 1049$) among 41,664 donors. Comparative analyses by sex, age, cause; χ^2 tests; logistic regression; synthesis of international reintegration interventions.

Results: ~60% of temporary deferrals were reversible (low Hb, medications, infections, immunizations); ~25% of permanent rejections were borderline or re-evaluable. Predictors of successful return included age <50 years, absence of chronic disease, regular donation history, and personalized medical follow-up.

Conclusion: A reintegration program for temporarily deferred and borderline rejected blood donors at the Regional Center of Transfusion Hematology – Burgas, including individualized donation intervals based on donor iron stores, targeted iron supplementation, digital donor status monitoring, and coordination with general practitioners, could restore a significant portion of the lost donor resource and improve the sustainability and efficiency of regional blood supply services.

Keywords: blood donation, donor deferral, reintegration, sustainability, ferritin-guided intervals.

Introduction

The blood supply is a critical component of public health and the security of the system. Its stability depends not only on recruiting new donors, but also on retaining and re-engaging existing donors. In Bulgaria, as in most European countries, the proportion of temporarily deferred donors ranges between 10–15%, while that of permanently deferred donors is 2–3%.

Experience shows that deferral from blood donation reduces donor confidence, creates a sense of rejection and failure, and increases the likelihood of long-term attrition. In this way, the system loses its most valuable resources - healthy and motivated volunteers.

Studies for the 2020–2024 period show a clear distinction between temporary medical reasons (anaemia,

infections, medications) and permanent contraindications (endocrine, cardiological, and oncological diseases). However, there is a gray area between them that, with appropriate medical re-evaluation and follow-up care, could serve as a source of a sustainable donor pool.

Materials and Methods

Data from 48,068 donors who underwent screening at the Regional Blood Transfusion Center – Burgas (2020–2024) were analyzed. Of these: 5,355 were temporarily deferred, 1,049 were permanently deferred, and 41,664 were approved and donated (Figure 1).

The data were stratified by gender, age, and reason. χ^2 tests for associations and logistic regression were used to assess the probability of reinstatement.

Figure 1

Results

The main reasons for temporary deferral from blood donation among the study participants were: low haemoglobin (29.7%), medication use (14.8%), hypertension (12.2%), infections (URI), vaccinations (9.3%),

and other less common reasons (34%). About 60% of these conditions are temporary and correctable (Figure 2).

Figure 2

The most common reasons for permanent exclusion from blood donation are: endocrine disorders (16.5%), cardiovascular diseases (13.1%), eye diseases (7.8%), skin diseases (5.4%), mental disorders (3.8%),

and other less common causes (53.4%). About 25% of cases are borderline - e.g., controlled hypertension, unsuitable veins, or eye diseases in remission.

Figure 3

Gender and Age

Women have a threefold higher rate of permanent rejection (5.2% compared to 1.8% for men). The highest-risk age groups are 41-55 years, which show a peak in both temporary deferrals and permanent rejections.

The ratio of deferred to actual donors shows that among men, approximately one in ten candidates is temporarily deferred, while among women, the relative proportion of deferred donors is higher. This is consistent with international observations indicating that female gender is a risk factor for temporary deferral,

particularly due to iron deficiency and low haemoglobin levels.

The data obtained underscore the need for a different approach to the two genders in the management of the donor pool. For women, strategies to prevent iron deficiency and longer intervals between donations should be implemented, while for men, the focus should be on controlling blood pressure and chronic diseases.

Figure 4

International Experience

Here we will present iron status management programs based on international experience.

Netherlands (Sanquin) – the introduction of ferritin-guided intervals reduces iron-deficiency-related complications by 40% and increases donor retention.

United Kingdom (INTERVAL trial) – tailoring intervals based on Hb/ferritin improves safety and retention.

Canada and the United States – post-donation iron supplementation (45 mg/day for 60 days) reduces rejection due to low Hb by 25%.

Behavioral Approaches

NHS Blood and Transplant (UK) – SMS and email reminders increase the likelihood of repeat donation by 15%.

Australian Lifeblood – digital pre-donation self-assessment questionnaires reduce unsuccessful donation attempts.

Coordination with GPs

The European Association for Transfusion Medicine recommends “letter-to-GP” programs—feedback to general practitioners regarding the management of hypertension, Hb, and ferritin—which increases the reintegration rate by 30% over 6 months.

Figure 5

Modules currently under development at the Burgas Regional Blood Transfusion Centre, including medical, digital, and behavioural modules.

Medical Module

The highest percentage of temporarily deferred donors is due to low haemoglobin, 1,590 out of a total of 5,355 deferred donors, or 29.7%. For these donors, **ferritin-guided donation intervals** are emerging as the most successful method internationally.

Ferritin-guided donation intervals are an approach to blood donation in which the interval between two donations is determined not only by the standard time interval but also by the level of ferritin in the donor’s body.

Ferritin is a protein that reflects iron stores in the body. It is the most sensitive indicator of early iron depletion, even when haemoglobin levels are still within the normal range (Figure 6).

In the Department of Transfusion Haematology in Burgas, the approach presented in Figure 6 was pilot-tested on 743 out of a total of 1,590 prospective donors who were temporarily deferred due to low haemoglobin levels measured prior to the blood donation. In 482 of these cases, the test showed a positive result, and these individuals remained regular blood donors on the condition of a longer interval between donations and a follow-up measurement of ferritin and haemoglobin one week prior to donation. This represents a 65% success rate for the method.

Figure 6

Hypertension at the time of blood donation is the third leading cause of temporary deferral of donors. For this reason, 651 out of a total of 5,355 prospective donors—or 12.2%—were deferred.

Management of hypertension using the “three good readings” protocol.

The “three good readings” protocol is a practical medical approach for evaluating donors with hypertension, requiring three consecutive blood pressure readings within acceptable limits to confirm that the condition is stable and controlled. The goal is to avoid unjustified permanent deferral, to distinguish temporary increases in blood pressure (stress, anxiety, “white coat effect”) from chronic uncontrolled hypertension, and to assess safety for both the donor and the recipient.

The donor is permitted to donate blood under the following conditions:

- in three separate measurements (during a single visit or multiple visits), the readings are within acceptable limits;
- there are no symptoms or complications;
- the condition is stabilized with medication, and no medication is being taken at the time of donation.

At the Department of Transfusion Haematology in Burgas, an experimental approach was applied to 190 prospective donors subject to temporary deferral due to high blood pressure measured prior to donation: rest, waiting for 1 hour within the department without any procedures, engaging their attention with positive video content, and attentive care from the staff of the Burgas Transfusion Haematology Department. The result is that among 46 people, blood pressure readings returned to normal after three measurements. The method achieved a success rate of 24.21%.

Figure 7

Digital Module

- Electronic file containing the reason for postponement and the date for reassessment.
- Automatic SMS reminders.
- Online self-assessment questionnaire before the appointment.

Behavioural module

- "Soft" nudges for selecting a date.
- Social messages ("85% of donors with low Hb return successfully").

- Micro-rewards (digital badges, recognition).

The digital and behavioural modules have currently been developed only in theory and have not been implemented in practice due to a lack of financial resources. Should funding become available, the accumulated database is ready to be put into practice immediately.

Figure 8

Expected Results and Indicators

Reintegration of 20–30% of temporarily deferred donors within 12–24 months. Reduction in iron-deficiency deferrals by $\geq 40\%$. Increase in active donors to

20 per 1,000 population (from 17 per 1,000 in 2024). Reduction in the shortage of blood components for elective surgeries by 10–15%.

Figure 9

Ethical and legal considerations relate to the voluntary nature and transparency of the reassessment; the storage of personal data in accordance with national legislation; informed consent for participation in a reintegration program; and monthly safety monitoring.

Discussion

The data confirm that the greatest potential for sustainability lies in the systematic management of temporarily deferred donors. The Bulgarian model of integrated healthcare (the existing link between the Regional Blood Transfusion Centres and primary care physicians) is a prerequisite for an effective national program.

The combination of medical re-evaluation, digital tracking, and behavioural approaches is fully in line with European practices. This strategy not only increases the donor pool but also improves the quality of the blood supply through controlled re-enrolment.

Conclusion

The reintegration of temporarily deferred and borderline rejected donors is a key measure for the stability of the transfusion system. Through the implementation of medical, digital, and organizational mechanisms, up to one-third of potentially lost donors can be recovered.

The introduction of a national registry, ferritin-based protocols, and partnerships with primary care is a realistic and safe path toward long-term self-sufficiency in the blood supply in Bulgaria.

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